

Optimal artificial neural network configurations for hourly solar irradiation estimation

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ABSTRACT

Solar energy is widely used in order to generate clean electric energy. However, due to its intermittent nature, this resource is only inserted in a limited way within the electrical networks. To increase the share of solar energy in the energy balance and allow better management of its production, it is necessary to know precisely the available solar potential at a fine time step to take into account all these stochastic variations. In this paper, a comparison between different artificial neural network (ANN) configurations is elaborated to estimate the hourly solar irradiation. An investigation of the optimal neurons and layers is investigated. To this end, feedforward neural network, cascade forward neural network and fitting neural network have been applied for this purpose. In this context, we have used different meteorological parameters to estimate the hourly global solar irradiation in the region of Laghouat, Algeria. The validation process shows that choosing the cascade forward neural network two inputs gives an R2 value equal to 97.24% and a normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) equals to 0.1678 compared to the results of three inputs, which gives an R2 value equal to 95.54% and an NRMSE equals to 0.2252. The comparison between different existing methods in literature show the goodness of the proposed models.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of the global economy has led to an unprecedented increase in fossil fuel consumption. This surge has simultaneously raised the costs and highlighted the finite nature of fossil fuel resources, prompting a search for alternative solutions [1]. Among these alternatives, renewable energy sources have emerged as a promising option. The sun, as Earth's primary source of energy [2], plays a crucial role in various forms of renewable energy, including solar photovoltaic, solar thermal, wind, geothermal, and hydroelectric power. Even hydrocarbon-generated energy can be considered a solar-derived energy, as it is ultimately the product of photosynthesis [3].

Solar irradiation provides an abundant, pollution-free energy source that has the potential to decrease our reliance on fossil fuels [4]. To effectively implement solar energy systems, it is crucial to accurately determine solar irradiation levels. Two primary methods are used for acquiring this data: ground-level measurements taken by meteorological networks [5] and radiometric stations across the globe [6], as well as

mathematical models for estimating data when direct measurements are unavailable [7]. These models utilize a variety of environmental and astronomical parameters, including ambient temperature, relative humidity, sunshine duration, solar declination, the length of the day, solar constant, variations in Earth-sun distance, and the average daily extraterrestrial irradiation on a horizontal plane at the atmosphere's boundary [8], [9]. This comprehensive approach ensures reliable data collection for solar energy applications.

In general, these models can be classified into three families [10]; semi-empirical models [11], spectral models [12], meteorological models [13]. The semi-empirical models have a local character and permit the direct, diffuse, and global components to be calculated. They use as input the meteorological variables (such as air temperature, sunshine period, and relative humidity) and geographical parameters (latitude, longitude, and altitude) [14]. They are based on regression relationships that can be usefully exploited to interpolate and therefore reconstitute solar irradiation data in locations with no measurements. The limitation of these models is that they are only applicable in clear sky situations. Moreover, meteorological models make it possible to calculate the global irradiation whatever the state of the sky using direct solar data collected in weather stations. They have the advantage of generating solar irradiation data for different inclined surfaces. Spectral models are primarily aimed at calculating the spectral components of solar irradiation on the ground. They are based on the determination of the transmission coefficients after attenuation by the various atmospheric constituents. They give exact results if you know the characteristics of certain atmospheric constituents, such as aerosols and clouds.

In addition, physical models [10], which consist of processing satellite images are images collected from the space stations that can be used to estimate the solar irradiation data. It allows the calculation of the amount of solar irradiation at any point in the world for different sky cases with high accuracy by analyzing satellite images. However, these models depend strongly on heavy mathematical modeling that needs a prior understanding of the dynamic behavior and the used parameters for each model. Hence, artificial intelligence models are proposed to overcome this problem. Kosovic *et al.* [15] speaks briefly of the performance of it is exhibited when applied to environmental data with the purpose of calculating solar irradiation. Recently, these models play a great role in estimating solar irradiation, ranging from neural network models as shown in Al-Ghussain *et al.* [16], where the results indicate that the developed models had better regression coefficients than fuzzy logic or metaheuristic optimization algorithms. They have proved to be a powerful tool to provide solar irradiation data [17].

In this paper, we aim to evaluate various artificial neural network (ANN) models for estimating hourly solar irradiation data. While ANNs are widely employed for tasks such as identification, classification, function approximation, and automatic control, their increasing use in data analysis has been observed, particularly as an effective alternative to conventional methods in numerous scientific areas, with a focus on meteorology and solar energy. These models require only a limited set of measured data, including temperature, solar altitude, wind speed, and other parameters.

The primary contributions of this study are twofold: first, we establish a benchmark of diverse neural network models suitable for estimation purposes, and second, we examine the impact of measured radiometric parameters during the estimation process to determine the influence of each parameter on the overall estimation model. To achieve this, we have experimented with various neural network configurations and architectures by adjusting the number of neurons and layers. Additionally, we employ error metrics to assess the accuracy and robustness of the optimal configurations for estimating solar irradiation data.

2. METHOD

This paper's primary goal is to explore various neural network types and configurations to estimate solar irradiation levels using diverse meteorological input data. The methodology employed in our study is depicted in Figure 1. A comprehensive explanation of each component within the proposed methodology is provided in the subsequent sections. By examining different neural network structures and configurations, we aim to determine the most effective approach to estimate solar irradiation based on the available meteorological inputs. This investigation will contribute to the ongoing efforts to harness solar energy more efficiently and effectively, supporting the transition to renewable energy sources.

2.1. Feedforward neural network

Feedforward neural networks, biologically-inspired classifiers, contain numerous neuron-like processing units arranged in layers. Each unit in a layer connects to those in the previous one, with varying weighted connections encoding the network's knowledge. These units are also known as nodes. Data flows from inputs through layers to outputs without feedback during standard operation, enabling the network to function as a classifier, hence the name "feedforward." Figure 2 illustrates a two-layer network with an output layer containing one unit and a hidden layer with two units. The network also features four input modules [18].

Figure 1. Flowchart of the adopted methodology

Figure 2. Different NN structures used in the adopted methodology

2.2. Cascade forward neural network

Cascading neural networks resemble feedback networks, with connections from input and prior layers to subsequent ones. Figure 2 shows a three-layer network where the output layer is directly connected to the input layer and hidden layer. Like feedback networks, cascading networks with two or more layers can learn arbitrary finite input-output relationships with sufficient hidden neurons. Applicable to any input-output mapping, these networks preserve linear relationships while also considering non-linear connections between inputs and outputs, offering a key advantage [19].

2.3. Fitting neural network

Fitting is the method of creating a curve or a mathematical function that is ideally fitted to a collection of previously collected points. Curve fittings may apply to both interpolations, where exact data points are needed to be smooth, where a flat function is designed to approximate the data. The estimated curves obtained from the data fitting can be used to help show the data, to predict the value of a function where no data are available, and to summarize the relationship between two or more variables [20].

3. DATA

For the estimation purpose, the city of Laghouat, Algeria (33.48° N, 2.51° E) is selected. Laghouat, experiences sweltering, arid summers and long, cold, dry, windy winters, with temperatures ranging from 1 °C to 39 °C. The brightest period is from April 19 until August 20, with solar irradiation exceeding 7.0 kWh/sq.m. The darkest period is from November 1 until February 5, with solar irradiation below 4.1 kWh/sq.m. Hourly global solar irradiation data for Laghouat is obtained from the SoDa [21] website and photovoltaic geographical information system (PVGIS) [22], which provide solar energy resource information and photovoltaic energy calculations for various regions.

4. SIMULATION RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The main objective is to test which neural network and architecture are the best to estimate the solar irradiation amount based on the measured data such as clear sky solar irradiation, temperature, sun height and others. To this end, a simulation is in order to test the performance and to judge the best architecture. Hence, an error metric is needed for this. For this, the error should be optimised. The accuracy of the considered models was tested by calculating the normalized mean squared error (NMSE), the root mean square error (RMSE), the normalized root mean squared error (NRMSE), coefficient of correlation (R) and the coefficient of determination (R^2). The next step consists of simulating two and three inputs using different neural network architecture and configuration. The objective is to make a full comparison between the networks. The error metrics were used for this comparison. The methodology consists of dividing the time series into training and testing sets. The testing one consists of selecting random days to collect 36 random days from the year and the left 11 months is chosen as a training set.

4.1. Case of 2 inputs

In this case, we have selected the clear sky and the top of atmosphere solar irradiation as inputs and the global solar irradiation amount as an output. The results are shown in Figure 3. Moreover, error metrics comparison between estimated and measured data is presented in Table 1.

From these tables, we can see clearly that the measured and estimated data are almost the same. Moreover, in the training phase, the selection of one layer with multiple neurons give the highest R^2 values for all the types of the used networks. In addition, in the testing phase, the same results were obtained, the selection of one layer with multiple neurons gives the best results compares to the multilayer and neurons selection.

4.2. Case of 3 inputs

In the same manner, we have selected three inputs namely; temperature, sun height, wind speed the obtained results are summarized in Table 2. From these results, we can confirm what we found in the case of two inputs. Most likely, the choice of one layer with multi neurons gives the best results compared to the case of multiple layers with neurons.

Figure 3. Comparison results between the measured data and estimated using fitting, feedforward and cascade forward neural networks for the case of 2 inputs

Table 3. Artificial intelligence methods for prediction of solar radiation from the literature and this study

Reference	Location	Models used	Inputs used	R ²
Xue <i>et al.</i> [23]	Beijing, China	Back propagation neural network (BPNN)	Temperature, sunshine duration, wind speed, rainfall, relative humidity, global solar irradiation and sunshine hours	0.8723
		BPNN- Genetic algorithm (GA)		0.8892
		BPNN-particle swarm optimization (PSO)		0.9082
Olatomiwa <i>et al.</i> [24]	Iseyin, Nigeria	Support vector machine (SVM)- Firefly algorithm (FFA)	Max and min temperature	0.8183
		ANN	Sunshine hours	0.7719
		Genetic programming (GP)		0.7784
Ramedani <i>et al.</i> [25]	Tehran, Iran	Support vector regression (SVR)- Radial basis function (RBF)	Sunshine hours, clear sky days, extraterrestrial irradiation, max and min temperature	0.8888
		SVR-Polynomial basis function (poly)		0.8669
		Adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS)		0.8988
		ANN		0.8939
Olatomiwa <i>et al.</i> [26]	Iseyin, Nigeria	ANFIS	Sunshine hours, min and max temperature	0.8543
Quej <i>et al.</i> [27]	Yucatán Peninsula, México	SVM	Max and min temperature	0.6684
		ANN	Rainfull	0.6483
		ANFIS	Extraterrestrial irradiation	0.6478
Zou <i>et al.</i> [28]	Changsha, China	Expanded-improved bristow-campbell model (E-IBCM)	Max and Min temperature, hydidity rainfull, air pressure and sunshine hours	0.9198
		Improved yang hybrid model (IYHM)		0.9348
		ANFIS		0.9698
Rahimikhoob [29]	Ahwaz, Iran	ANN	Extraterrestrial irradiation	0.7903
Benghanem and Melit [30]	AlMadinah, Saudi Arabia	Radial basis function neural network (RBFNN)	Temperature	0.9600
		Multilayer perception (MLP)	Sunshine hours	0.8960
Jiang <i>et al.</i> [31]	China	Deep learning (DL)	MTSAT imagery	0.88
Ağbulut <i>et al.</i> [32]	Turkey (Kırklareli, Tokat, Nevşehir and Karaman)	ANN	Max and min temperature, extraterrestrial irradiation, sunshine hours	from
		SVM		0.855
		DL		to
Woldegiyorgis <i>et al.</i> [33]	Ethiopia	Kernel and nearest-neighbor (k-NN)	Cloud cover	0.936
		Feed-forward neural network (FFNN)	Temperature, sunshine duration, wind speed, rainfall, relative humidity,	0.7998
Geetha <i>et al.</i> [34]	Tamil Nadu, India	ANN (levenberg-marquardt (LM); scaled conjugate gradient (SCG); resilient backpropagation (RP))	Wind speed	0.8790
Kurniawan and Harumwidiah [35]	Surabaya, Indonesia	ANN	Temperature	
			Humidity	
Bounoua <i>et al.</i> [36]	Morocco	MLP(FFNN)	Wind speed, temperature, humidity, clouds and date	0.9670
			Wind speed temperature, humidity	0.9254

5. CONCLUSION

This study focuses on using ANNs to develop artificial intelligence models for predicting global solar irradiation. Astronomical and meteorological parameters are utilized to estimate solar irradiation in Laghouat, Algeria. The best model is chosen based on its predictive accuracy. We have examined the possibility of estimating hourly global solar irradiation from several models by entering astronomical and metrological parameters using different neural networks. We tried several combinations of the input data and networks configurations. We found that the combination of tow input (the clear sky and the top of atmosphere solar irradiation) with 12 neurons of the hidden layer is the one that gives the best results, for this combination, the correlation coefficient between the global solar irradiation measured and that estimated is 97.24% for the test data. It was concluded that this model may be preferred for estimating solar irradiation intensities for the studied site and for other places with similar climatic conditions. Future works can test another type of neural networks, namely; the hybrid combination between the models. The use of optimisation techniques can be also implemented in order to optimise the number of neurons and layers for optimal results.

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